

CROSS-CULTURAL RELATIONS AND BUSINESS CULTURE IN GEORGIA

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Bondo GASVIANI¹,
Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia

ABSTRACT. The present study "Cross-cultural relations and business Culture in Georgia" is dedicated to the Analysis of specifics of Georgian business culture according to the several characteristics of the value factors compiled by Geert Hofstede (1980, 1984) and Fons Trompenaars (1994). Prepared questionnaires related to the main characteristics of the culture (Power distance, individualism / collectivism, uncertainty avoidance rate, masculinity / femininity, universalism - particularism, neutral / emotional, specific (special) / diffuse, achievement and ascription culture and Time Attitude) Selective interviews were conducted with up to 50 respondents who were foreign nationals and owned a business or were employed in the Georgian labor market. As a result of the research, the peculiarities of the Georgian business-cultural phenomenon have been identified, which foreign entrepreneurs must take into account in order to effectively operate in the mentioned market.

The conclusions and recommendations will help all those who are interested in doing business in Georgia and will facilitate the effective implementation of business communications in the country.

Keywords: *Culture, Cross-Culture, Business-Communication, Business Negotiation, International Business*

Introduction. Modern business is impossible to imagine without a proper understanding of cross-cultural problems and their adequate cognition. As a result of globalization, business transnationalization has established a cultural factor priority in the field of business relationships, whereupon, the study of cross-cultural differences became the basis of successful business activity. The formation of human awareness is based on the knowledge, beliefs, morals, laws, values, norms and on the basis of the habits which they acquire in conducting public coexistence and conducting joint material activities. Consequently, only with the correct knowledge of a society with different cultural values and norms, with the correct perception of its traditions, successful business activities are possible. Culture is one of the main components of business and it has influence on its strategic directions, management, decision-making process and all business functions. Business culture is reflected in activities such as: meetings, negotiations, formalities, use of social media, location of office, etc. Business culture is connected to behavior, ethics, and etiquette. It presents the values, vision, work style, beliefs and habits of the organization.

The formation of the business culture of any country is impacted by the environment in which a certain society lives. Prerequisite for the formation of a society is the geographical and climatic conditions of the country, demographic status, linguistic affiliation, expression of self-identification, stratified castes and clusters in it. In the context of cross-cultural business relations, an objective assessment of certain characteristics of a country is especially important.

In view of all the above, the study of the characteristics of the Georgian business culture became important. For this, we have used the cultural characteristics of Hofstede and Trompenaars that give a general idea of the peculiarities of business culture. Due to the urgency of the research the following questions were formed:

¹ **Bondo GASVIANI**, Ph.D. in Business Administration, The Faculty of Business, Technology and Education, Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia, m e-Mail: bondo.gasviani@iliauni.edu.ge, +995577380204, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0763-5028>

- Which of the respondents' representatives are interested in doing business in Georgia;
- What kind of business activities are held in the Georgian market;
- Duration of their activities and dimensions of enterprises;
- Factors to consider when organizing business and negotiations in Georgia.

In view of all the above, the characteristics established by Hofstede (1980, 1984) and Trompenaars (1994) were analyzed and systematized. The main part of the paper discusses each characteristic and the results of their research (characteristics of other countries) which is compared with the Georgian reality. Where the result of the research is graphically represented and analyzed its impact on business processes. Thus, the data of our study are compared with the results of similar studies, the differences are analyzed and the relevant conclusions are made.

1. Literature review

Cultural understanding is a key issue in the development of cross-cultural relationships and is one of the major issues facing multi-national organizations both internally within their human resource development and externally with the numerous relationships they develop with buyers and suppliers in many different international countries (Tse, Lee, Vertinsky and Wehrung 1988). Yet, although these issues have been highlighted previously (see Ajiferuke and Boddewyn 1970; Adler 1983; Bhaghat and McQuaid 1982; Smircich 1983) the academic community is still grappling with these contentious issues. With insufficient progress being made towards cultural research, especially cultural studies external to the United States, more research needs to be conducted. Aspects of cross-cultural business relations are widely discussed in recent scientific literature. (Lowe, Purchase & Veludo, 2002, p.2) In modern business literature, media and Internet sources the peculiarities of this or that country are reflected in the process of business activity (Team management, leading style, negotiation, etc.).

However, it should be noted that Georgian culture is less studied in terms of business relations, team management and generally only in unit cases it is discussed in the context of cross-cultural business relations.

Based on the obtained scientific research, published literature and other available materials (information), we have found that the characteristics of business culture are undergoing some changes in parallel with the process of globalization. However, the study of key factors requires constant monitoring and consideration of the implementation process in the country, especially at the initial stage when there is a primary contact with local cultures.

Dutch researcher of organizational culture typology, scientist, professor of anthropology Geert Hofstede conducted research from 1960 to 1980 in 70 countries around the world. More than 60,000 respondents were interviewed about their satisfaction with their work, colleagues, leading, life goals, perception of labor process problems, and professional priorities. In addition, he took into account gender-age and professional (work experience, profession) indicators. National-state and ethnic factors were considered as the criteria of this typology. He constructed a four-factor value model (1980) and identified the following key characteristics: power distance, individualism / collectivism, uncertainty avoidance rate, masculinity / femininity. All four dimensions of culture are closely interacting, and based on and combining them, it is possible to identify important characteristics such as the management style of a given organization, potentially probability of unleashing conflicts, the nature of their course and the means of solving them. Based on these data, a conclusion can be made about the compatibility of organizations and possible outcomes.

G. Hofstede research is widely accepted. Nevertheless, a certain "weakness" of the structure stimulates the use of other approaches. The research of a Holland scientist Fons Trompenaars (1994) has found wide recognition. He singled out five cultural variables that can be considered G. Hofstede's indices analogous. These characteristics are: universalism - particularism, individualism - collectivism, neutral and emotional cultures, specific and diffuse cultures, achievement and

ascription culture (belonging to a group). F. Trompenaars also paid special attention to the commandment of time and its attitude toward it. In this regard, he notes the existence of two approaches: consistent (American) and synchronous (Mexican).

The scientific findings of Trompenaar have not been widely criticized. However, some researchers point to a number of defects in the Trompenaarsian classification of business culture. For example, his research has been criticized for being too territorial. Finally, it is noteworthy that in the survey there were the lack of situational tests used, which lies in the fact that the researcher offers the respondent in advance possible options for behavior, so the researcher restricts the respondent's freedom of expression.

Nevertheless, assessing the cultural and value side of the impact on the organizational environment and the competitiveness of the company is one of the most important issues for modern management. Trompenaars's research has given us a lot of information on how to do business in different countries.

Georgian scientific literature on the study of cross-cultural business relations is very poor, but in this regard, the article "Cultural Values and Georgian Society in Business Communication" published in 2015 in the journal *Education and Humanities* by the Georgian professor Maia Kutateladze is noteworthy. In this article she discusses and analyzes several important features of the cultural values of Georgian society according to the criteria established by Hofstede and Trompenaars. According to the article, Georgian society is characterized by a high power distance, one can always feel deep respect and reverence towards superiors and elders. It is very difficult to specifically attribute Georgian culture to the individual or the collective, as individual achievements are valued in the country, although kinship is also important. Living without belonging to a particular group, membership, is actually impossible. Georgians are characterized by a high rate of avoidance of uncertainty, they are less risk-averse and prefer clarity and security in business. According to masculinity / femininity, Georgian culture is characterized as strongly masculine, with small traits of femininity. He tends to be more particular, so relationships are very important and involving a relative or family member in the business is natural and acceptable, even if it is against certain rules. We Georgians are very emotional, which in many cases is not hidden. Georgian people are very diffuse, people who meet in one work environment often become close friends, sometimes they even make relative connections between others. Achievements are valued, however ascription is still characterizing and belonging to a particular group gives certain advantages. As for time management, Georgians love to do everything at the last second, even though they try to be punctual, a 10-15 minute delay is acceptable to them (Kutateladze, 2015).

2. Data and Methodology

For in-depth study and practical support of the arguments, as mentioned above, we conducted an interview-questionnaire in the local market with about 50 foreign nationals who owned a business or were employed in the Georgian labor market. The results of the research reflected the opinions, problems and recommendations of entrepreneurs and / or employees in almost all major economic sectors. The representativeness of the survey results was also conditioned by the fact that the survey concerned enterprises of different sizes and duration of activities. In particular, according to the number of employees, 83.3% of the respondents surveyed are employed in small enterprises (up to 50 employees), 5.6% - in medium enterprises (employs 50 to 250 employees), and 11.1% - in large ones. (Number of employees exceeds 249). As for the annual turnover, the turnover of 88.9% of the enterprises that owned or operated was less than 12 million GEL, while 11.1% exceeded 60 million GEL. One of the important criteria for the research is the duration of operation in Georgia. It was found that 55.6% of the above-mentioned enterprises have been operating in the Georgian market for less than three years, 27.8% for 3-5 years, 16.7% for more than 5 years.

3. The Model and Findings

The aim of the research was to determine the representatives of which countries are engaged in business activities in Georgia. The results are distributed as follows (Figure 1):

Fig. 1. Foreigners engaged in business in Georgia by nationality

Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

According to the analysis of the Figure, a large part of foreign businessmen belongs to the representatives of the countries included in the clusters of South-Eastern Europe, Eastern Europe and the Middle East. Georgia has a historical connection with these countries (50.0% of the former USSR). The interest of American, British and Iranian entrepreneurs toward Georgia is also noteworthy.

The most interesting cultural value especially in business is the distance of power. It is connected to how much culture encourages leaders to use power. A high index of power distance means recognizing that hierarchy is naturally unequal, orders are not obeyed, power prevails over law, top management is not available, employees are afraid to express their opinion, they trust less each other. Low index, in turn, means that inequality of roles is quite pronounced in the organization, while hierarchical leadership is focused on the style of convenient management of employees, law prevails over power, higher management is available, it is enough to redistribute power to change the existing hierarchy; There is a hidden harmony between managers and subordinates, and solidarity between ordinary employees. Culture with a high degree of power distance is typical for France and India for example, while culture with a low power distance index is typical for Austria and Israel (Hofstede 1980).

The views of the respondents were equally divided in this case (See Figure 2). In fact, it has been confirmed that "Georgian society is inclined to the distance of high power, always feels awe and respect for leaders and superiors. Although Georgians are very sociable and the workplace is no exception, it is possible to see more informal relations with both superiors and leaders (Kutateladze 2015).

Fig. 2. Characteristics of Georgian Culture Distance of power

Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

Another characteristic that clearly expresses cultural differences is individualism and collectivism. The parameter evaluates the degree of integration of individuals into groups. Individualism means that a person acts in the interests of both himself and the people closest to him, so in the interests of relatives. Individualist culture (e.g., USA, England) emphasizes personal initiative and

achievement, and everyone has the right to personal life and opinion. Collectivism (Iran, Peru), on the other hand, holds that all people by birth or work belong to a more or less close group and has no right to consider himself separate from it. The group cares about its members and they, in turn, make every effort to ensure its well-being. In an individualistic culture the ideal is a good leader (Hofstede, 1980; Trompenaars, & Hampden-Turner 1994).

Judging by the results of the survey, it is difficult to clearly define which characteristic of Georgian society belongs. 27.8% of respondents consider them individualists, 11.1% perceive them as a collective society, 27.8% attribute both characteristics, and 33.3% find it difficult to answer (Figure 3).

Fig. 3. Characteristics of Georgian culture according to individualism / collectivism
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

Individualism is valued in Georgia, some people have benefits. But society also has a close connection with collectivism, because Georgians are very close to their relatives and living without belonging to a small group literally makes no sense. It is noteworthy that individualistic cultures believe in the existence of universal values that must be shared. Some Georgians believe that the way of life they go through individually is preferable. Most share the belief of collectivism that different groups may have different values (Kutateladze 2015).

Another difference between cultures is the rate of avoidance of uncertainty. Cultures with a high rate of avoidance of uncertainty feel uncomfortable because of risk and uncertainty and use multiple rituals, routines and bureaucracies (Japan, Argentina, France). Risk in the society of low rate of avoidance of uncertainty is acceptable and more informality and flexibility is observed in business communication (Hofstede 1980). The results of the survey gave us a different picture (from Kutateladze 2015), unequivocally Georgians can be attributed to a society with a low culture of avoiding the risk of uncertainty, 88.9% of respondents believe that they are informal in business relationships, they are flexible and love to take risks. Only 11.1% of respondents believe that they are characterized by a high level of avoidance of uncertainty, although it is noteworthy that in this case the majority of respondents work as consultants, or implement projects of donor organizations in the public sector, which is characterized by bureaucracy and routine (Figure 4).

Fig. 4. Characteristics of Georgian culture according to uncertainty avoiding
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

Masculinity and femininity are cultural dimensions that reflect a culture's tendency to follow the style of male or female behavior. The name of this parameter is related to the traditional representation of the social roles of women and men. The man is usually committed to demonstrating strength, on the production of livelihoods while the woman should be engaged in improving the quality of life and caring for the weak. Accordingly, the role of men in relation to the organization means "life for work", or orientation to achieve the goal, and the role of women - work "for life" or orientation to accomplish the task. Consequently, in "masculine" cultures, the humanization of labor is perceived as an opportunity for recognition, self-realization, and career building. In "feminine" cultures, the humanization of labor is seen as the existence of constant attention to employees, good relations between members of the organization. Examples of "masculine" culture are Austria, Italy and "feminine" are the Netherlands, Sweden.

"Masculine" and "feminine" cultures choose different ways of solving problems. Where "feminine" values predominate, preference is given to group decision-making, while in "masculine" culture, individual effort is preferred. Ways of resolving conflicts also depend on the nature of the culture. In "masculine" organizations, the conflict is open and strict, which usually reaches a logical end, while in "feminine" organizations it is more often disguised, has latent nature and solution is made by non-violent methods, but in the process of discussion, negotiations (Hofstede 1980).

The results of the research show (Figure 5) that Georgian culture is significantly masculine (88.9% of respondents), with very few traits of femininity. Georgians love competition, success and money, but on the other hand they are people who care a lot about others and more or less support them (Kutateladze 2015).

Fig. 5. Characteristics of Georgian Culture Masculinity / femininity

Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

One of the characteristics of the differences between cultures is particularism or relationship-based and universalism or rule-based cultures. Universalism is the belief that ideas and practices can be applied everywhere, without change. Specialization arose from the belief that circumstances dictate how ideas and practices should be applied. Cultures with a high universalism index focus more on formal rules than on relationships. Business contracts are considered very narrow because people think that "a deal is a deal". In low-value cultures of universalism, the focus is on relationships and trust rather than formal rules. In such cultures, contracts change frequently, and because partners know each other much better, depending on the circumstances they often change the way to achieve results (Trompenaars, & Hampden-Turner, 1994).

In Trompenaars's early studies was found that the United States, Australia, Germany, Sweden, and the United Kingdom were with a high value of the Universalism Index, while Venezuela, the CIS, Indonesia, and China were low.

On question how Georgians are characterized in this regard, 55.6% of respondents believe that Georgians are more inclined to particularism, 38.8% found it difficult to give a specific answer, and only 5.6% perceive Georgians as universalists (Figure 6).

Fig. 6. Characteristics of Georgian Culture Particularism / universalism
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

In fact, we can conclude that particularism is characteristic of Georgian culture and it is based more on relationships. In Georgia, it is accepted (in some cases even mandatory) to involve a friend or family member in business, although this may be against certain rules. In contrast to a rule-based society, where a businessman "can invest in family or friends, but this is not a general model and this can lead to more tensions that relationships can withstand" (Kutateladze 2015). Thus, it is clear that international business demands of knowledge of the nature of obedience to the rules of society somehow.

One of the interesting dimensions is Neutral and Emotional cultures. In neutral cultures, emotion control is accepted. In this field similar approaches have such different cultures as Japanese and English. Representatives of these nations do not express their feelings. They calmly deal with difficulties. Otherwise representatives of emotional cultures express their feelings openly and naturally. They are mostly noisy and sociable. According to Trompenaars, representatives of emotional culture include Mexicans, Dutch, and Swiss. Their restraint does not constitute support for projects or lack of interest. Rather, it may indicate a focus on the issue. On the other hand, representatives of a neutral culture should adequately respond to openness and emotionality, while at the same time not overestimating the importance of strong expression of feelings (Trompenaars, & Hampden-Turner, 1994).

According to the results of the survey Georgians can be attributed to emotional culture, 88.9% of respondents believe that they are very emotional and sometimes that's cannot be hidden. During negotiations Georgians can be quite emotional talkers - the tone of voice may increase and gestures may become more active. Only 11.1% of respondents attributes them to representatives of a neutral culture, but it is noteworthy, that in this case the majority of respondents were members of no less emotional cultures as the Italians, the Spaniards and the Greeks (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. Characteristics of Georgian Culture Neutral / Emotional
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

When starting a cross-cultural business, it is important to determine whether the culture is specific or diffuse. Special culture implies a strict separation of a person's public and private space. Representatives of a special culture try to expand their own public space, they are happy to share it with others and easily get in touch. At the same time, they are quite strict about protecting their

personal life and share it only with close friends and colleagues. Diffuse culture is characterized by a combination of public and private spaces. Representatives of this type of culture are stricter with regard to public space, since its accessibility means personal penetration. According to empirical studies, countries with special cultures include the United Kingdom, the United States, and Switzerland. Diffuse culture dominates in Venezuela, China and Spain (Trompenaars et al, 1994).

88.9% of respondents believe that Georgian culture is diffuse, only 11.1% attribute it to specific (Figure 8). So we can confirm that Georgian people are diffuse in relations. People who work together often become very close friends, sometimes even relatives or get married. Diffuse cultures are characterized by less workforce mobility and a greater focus on company success. They also value solitude and the personal, but fully or almost completely "living alone causes alienation and superficiality" (Kutateladze 2015).

Fig. 8. Characteristics of Georgian culture according to specific / diffuse
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

An important feature of culture is the focus on achievement and belonging. The culture of achievement is characterized by the fact that the status of a member of the community is determined by the successful performance of his functions. Belonging status culture is determined by a person belonging to a particular group on the basis of kinship or professional sign (Trompenaars et al, 1994). Trompenaars (1994) attributed the culture of achievement to Austria, USA, Great Britain, Switzerland, Mexico, Germany. Attribution-oriented indicators characterize Venezuela, Indonesia, Chile, CIS countries.

The recommendations of the Trompenaars (1994) for the interaction of the representatives of this type of culture are as follows: in order to work in the countries of the respective cultures, it is necessary to select the most authoritative individuals to establish partnerships, who have high status due to age, social ties, etc. (Relevant information, technical experts, etc.). To ensure a favorable climate in a country with a culture of achievement, you need to convince your partners that your team is staffed and professionally competent (has relevant information, has technical experts, etc.).

The diversity of Georgian society and its aspiration for equal human capabilities make it difficult for it to belong to achievement-oriented or belonging-oriented cultures. According to the survey, 16.7% of respondents consider it achievement-oriented, 22.2% perceive it as attribution-oriented, while 61.1% find it difficult to give a specific answer and believe that both characteristics are equally felt in society (Figure N9).

Fig. 9. Characteristics of Georgian culture, orientation towards achievement / belonging
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

In achievement-oriented cultures, people are judged by their achievements and the successful performance of their assigned functions. Georgian society remembers and appreciates human merit for a long time. However, belonging orientation is not unusual in Georgia. Belonging means giving status with something like birth, kinship, gender, age, personal connections, or educational attainment. This is not a bad practice, however, its excessive use can lead to unintended consequences not only in business, but also can create some problems in human rights.

In addition to the above, another important feature of comparing cultures is the approach to time. In terms of time management there are consistent and synchronous cultures. Consistent cultures such as North Americans, English, Germans, and others typically focus on each item on the agenda. They believe that the individual can have an impact on the future, but there are plenty of opportunities and making the right decision is vital. Thus, they are more focused on short-term planning in business. Representatives of synchronous cultures such as Southern Europe, South America, Asia time is seen as a kind of section from the past, present and future. More precisely, “time is flexible and different activities can be carried out at the same time. Representatives of synchronous culture have a goal, but there is no single “critical way” to achieve this goal. There are many ways to achieve a goal and one can switch between activities as needed” It is these factors that affect the ability to meet deadlines (Trompenaars et al, 1994). 88.9% of the respondents describe Georgians as representatives of synchronous culture and think that they are less punctual and mostly procrastinators - The case is completed by the last second (see Figure N10). This in itself affects their strategic thinking and business development. They usually have long-term plans and feel uncomfortable with short-term planning. This is also a problem as the development of modern, especially international business is more focused on short-term planning, as it is difficult to find solid ground or stable demand for one type of business with limitless diversity. Especially if we take into account the socio-political and economic situation of the country, the unstable social environment, the high degree of regular legislative changes and the creeping occupation create additional problems in the long-term strategic planning and execution of the plan.

Fig. 10. Characteristics of Georgian culture in the approach to time
Source: Compiled based on the results of surveys conducted by the author.

Time management skills also affect punctuality, Georgians generally try to be punctual, although a 10 or 15-minute delay is natural and acceptable. Restraint should not be left without attention, which is the biggest challenge for Georgians.

Doing business in Georgia, as in many other countries, is not easy in some contexts. Here people have an individual pace of culture that is foreign to other countries, their timeliness, expressiveness, and ability to obey the law can be confusing, but their sociable, managerial, and caring nature truly has fertile ground for promising, successful and profitable business communication. Which is a good foundation for a promising and profitable partnership. There are many small things in interpersonal and business relationships in Georgia (Kutateladze,2015). Local environment has a significant impact on building long-term mutually beneficial relationships.

Georgian business culture is less formal compared to other countries. Therefore, in the sources published by various foreign researchers and businessmen, we come across the following theses and advice for those who plan or have business relations in Georgia (Georgian Journal, 2011):

- Shake hand to everyone when meeting and saying goodbye;
- Maintain eye contact when greeting, speaking. Avoiding the eye contact is perceived as hiding something or telling a lie;
- Georgians do not avoid of expressing emotions. Do not be surprised if you witness the manifestation of anger at a business meeting;
- Georgians can be quite emotional talkers. During speech, the tone of voice may increase and gestures may become more active;
- Although Georgians are distinguished by kindness and kindness, they can be quite direct and direct in arguing;
- At the beginning of the meeting, the attendees are introduced according to the hierarchy (leaders) and age, women are introduced first;
- Be prepared to talk in detail about your education, professional experience and the purpose of the visit;
- At the very first meeting you will be watching the possibility of establishing a business relationship. Do not wait for any contract to be signed immediately. Be patient, this step takes time;
- Meetings can be in the form of lunch or dinner. The topics of conversation will be far from business issues, but they are very important as the Georgian hosts try to get to know the partner on a personal level;
- In most cases, all decisions are made at the highest level of the company;
- The meeting can often be delayed by external problems. It should not be understood as if the host is not interested in a particular issue, Georgians simply do not see the difficulties in doing several things at the same time;
- In business relations with Georgians, their lack of punctuality should be taken into account. Being late as an early departure from work is accepted event here;
- Trade with Georgians is not even possible but necessary. The practice of discounts and concessions is widely spread and common here;
- Subordinate watching from above is not accepted in Georgia. In this case leader may be considered as a despot or a tyrant;
- If you learn a few words in Georgian, you can gain the goodwill of your Georgian partners.

Conclusions

Overall, despite the process of economic and social transformation in the country, the particularism is still high, it is more relationship-based. People try to deal with the uncertainty of the future in different ways. Frequency of stress and tension, health status are important elements for assessing the avoidance of uncertainty, the level of which is low in Georgian society. Elements of masculinity dominate for Georgian society. With the Georgian mentality, national traditions must be adapted to a new environment, which indicates a long-term orientation of culture. Our culture is characterized by high contextually.

Based on the above, foreign entrepreneurs should take into account the following features of the Georgian cross-cultural phenomenon:

- Georgian society is based on the foundations of individualism as a result of modernization and transformation. Therefore, the individual achievements of employees in the process of encouragement, promotion should be taken into account;
- The pursuit of individualism and the low level of avoidance of uncertainty give us reason to conclude that high hierarchy and inflexible management style do not work effectively in our

country. It is important for the international manager to show an encouraging attitude towards local workers' initiatives;

- Due to the low level of avoidance of uncertainty, the introduction of new technologies in Georgia and the entry of new products into the market will increase the competitiveness of companies;

- International managers need to connect motivation to masculine values;

- Due to the socio-cultural peculiarities revealed in Georgia, the cross-cultural factor hindering international business relations is the low level of trust. Therefore, it is important for foreign businessmen to establish an atmosphere of mutual trust.

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